

Self-evaluation: A method for the assessment of scientific output

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Abstract

We asked social science researchers to state their top 3 publications. 2,331 academics who work in 42 countries responded to the survey. The respondents' Google Scholar and Scopus profiles, and their biographical information are also collected. Preliminary results show that 17% of the top 3 publications are not indexed in Scopus. The ratio of the top 3 publications that are not indexed in Scopus is 74% for books and 83% for non-English publications. The best publications have more citations than the second and third-best publications in Scopus, but the same result cannot be attained when Google Scholar citations are used. This is still a project in progress. When the project is completed, we aim to fully analyze the self-evaluations by the bibliometric data and incorporate this information to improve the assessment of scientific output.

Introduction

The publications are mostly evaluated by outsiders. The referees and editors decide whether a publication is to be accepted to a prestigious journal. The citations—mention of the publications by other researchers—are used as the primary bibliometric metric to evaluate the quality of the publications. The authors of a publication typically spend more time on their research than outsiders who evaluate their work, therefore authors may have more information—for example, the accuracy of the data used—than outsiders.

There is clear evidence that social scientists are not treated equally under the citation-based metrics. Social science journals are not as easily indexed as science journals in the publication indices such as Web of Science (Demarchi & Lorenzetti, 2016). Social science publications are more likely to be conducted in languages other than English, and the language barrier is another reason for receiving fewer citations (Van Raan et al., 2011). As a result, an average social science publication receives fewer citations than an average science publication (Yuret, 2018). The under-evaluation can be an important problem for social scientists. For example, a dean who decides on the academic promotion of a scientist and a social scientist may have difficulty in attributing the citation differences to their academic fields.

This is still an ongoing project. The project aims to incorporate information attained from self-evaluations to attain a fairer assessment of scientific output. We confine our query to social scientists who would benefit more from a fairer assessment.

Data

In the survey, the social scientists are asked to name their top 3 publications (Question A), and the source that covers their complete publication records (Question B). These two questions are stated as follows.

Question A: Could you please name your top three publications (published in 2011-2020) according to your self-assessment, in descending order (i.e., first publication is your best)? It is sufficient if you can give a short title and publication year of your publications.

Question B: Could you please give me the source where I can find your rather complete list of publications (published in 2011-2020)? Possible sources that come to my mind are your home

page in your institution, your personal home page (e.g., google sites), and publication indices (e.g. google scholar). If the list is not complete in any of the sources that I can access, could you please attach the list in response to this e-mail?

We e-mailed 32,573 researchers who work in the economics, political science, psychology, and sociology departments of the top 500 universities according to Shanghai Rankings, and asked them to answer Questions A&B.¹ We sent two rounds of emails. We manually sent individual emails in the first round to maximize the response rate and sent bulk emails in the second round. Despite these efforts, we only received 2,331 responses (7.2% response rate). Nevertheless, researchers from various backgrounds located in 42 different countries contributed their self-evaluations as shown in Table 1. The response rates do not change significantly among academic fields (Highest: Psychology 7.8%, Lowest: Political Science: 6.3%), and the response rate for universities in the top 200 is about the same as the universities that are ranked below 200 (both rates are rounded to 7.2%).

Table 1. Response rates and the number of responses by country

High Response Rate (>10%)
Austria(31), Brazil(64), Chile(12), Czech(9), Estonia(6), France(50), Germany(158), Ireland(14), Israel(34), Italy(320), Macau(3), Malaysia(5), New Zealand(11), Poland(27), Portugal(20), Sweden(64), Switzerland(48)
Medium Response Rate (5%, 10%)
Australia(123), Belgium(23), Canada(100), Egypt(3), Finland(5), Greece(4), Hong Kong(12), Mexico(10), Netherlands(64), Norway(37), Russia(35), Singapore(6), South Africa(17), Spain(161), United States(594)
Low Response Rate (<5%)
Argentine(3), China(56), Denmark(14), Iran(2), Japan(19), Korea(17), Saudi Arabia(1), Taiwan(6), Turkey(3), United Kingdom(140)

Note: The countries are ordered alphabetically within each category, and the number of responses from each country is given in parentheses.

We selected our sample from academics who are at least associate professors (senior lecturers in the UK system) so that they are likely to be active in publishing within the time frame (2011-2020). As a result, 87% of our respondents got their PhD before 2010. 37% of the respondents are female.

We collected the Google Scholar (GS) and Scopus profiles of all respondents. GS has more coverage, and Scopus has more accuracy (e.g. fewer double entries) and more information (e.g. document types of the publications). 1969 respondents have GS profiles that are readily available. We constructed GS profiles of 358 respondents by searching all their publications in GS from the source given in their answer to Question B. Only four respondents do not have any publications that have GS entries. 43 respondents do not have any publications that are indexed in Scopus, and this number increases to 58 when publications within the time frame are considered.

The percentile rankings within the academic category that are given by Scimago are used for journal rankings.² If the journal belongs to more than one category, we take the average of the percentiles from those categories.

¹The rankings are attained from <<http://www.shanghairanking.com/rankings/arwu/2021>>

²Scimago rankings are available from <<https://www.scimagojr.com/journalrank.php>>

Response to Question B

Question B asks the respondents a source that gives their full list of publications. 54% of the respondents named a database, 36% stated the website of their institution, 17% attached their publications, 15% gave the address of their private page, and 2% did not answer the question. Since there are respondents who have given multiple answers (e.g. attached a CV and named a database at the same time), the total exceeds 100%. Some respondents who stated the institutional web page specifically mentioned the database within the institutional web page (e.g. IRIS in Italian universities), some respondents point out the CVs that are located under their institutional web page, others simply state the address of their institutional web page without giving any specific instruction.

Among 1270 respondents who named a database, 758 chose to state GS. The framing of Question B is partly responsible for this high number because GS is given as an example of a publication index. Other popular answers are Orcid (121 respondents), Researchgate (97), and Scopus (68). There are also national databases (such as Lattes (44)). The low ratio of journal-specific databases can be explained by the fact that books are an important part of social science publications.

Question A. Extended time frame

The first interesting note about the answers to Question A is that respondents did not stay within the time frame (2011-2020). The time frame is restricted to no later than 2020 because citation statistics cannot be used properly for later publications. The time frame is restricted to years after 2011 because some respondents would not be publishing actively before that year. Moreover, keeping the time frame to ten years eased the construction of missing GS profiles, and make our results valid for a more current period. However, many respondents chose to ignore the time restriction without even mentioning this issue in their responses.

509 respondents (22%) chose at least one publication after 2020, and 146 respondents (6%) chose at least one publication before 2011 as one of their top 3 publications. Although we noted that answers outside of the time frame are acceptable in the second round of e-mails, the ratio of out-of-time frame answers stayed the same. The ratio of those who have responded outside of the time frame does not change by the academic field either (Range is between 27% and 29%). It is also not likely the case that the respondents picked out-of-time frame publications because they do not have enough publications. For example, psychology respondents who gave all their answers within the time frame have an average of 51 publications, those who chose a publication before 2011 have an average of 41 publications, and those who picked a publication after 2020 have an average of 48 publications in Scopus that are published from 2011 to 2020. When we construct GS and Scopus profiles to include those years that the respondents picked. For example, if a respondent chooses a 2022 publication for one of their top 3 publications, we constructed the profiles within 2011-2022.

GS and Scopus profiles

Table 2 gives the scientific output of respondents categorized in their academic fields. We only consider the publications within the time frame (2011-2020 or extended by the response). From the third and fourth columns of the table, we see that 2,331 respondents have a total of 137,574 publications indexed in GS and 70,165 publications indexed in Scopus.

The total number of publications of each respondent is divided by the number of years in the time frame to find their publications per year. Then, the total publications per year within each

field is divided by the total number of respondents within each field to find the productivity in the field. The fifth and sixth columns of Table 2 give the productivity of respondents in GS and Scopus, respectively. We see that psychologists are more productive in both measures. This is not surprising as the productivity differences among academic fields are well documented (Yuret, 2015).

The number of citations of a publication is divided by the number of years that have passed to find the year-adjusted number of citations. The seventh and eighth columns of Table 2 give the year-adjusted number of GS and Scopus citations, respectively. We see that the highest GS and Scopus citation performance is attained by psychologists.

In the last column of Table 2, the journal ranks from Scimago are used, and average journal publication percentiles for publications indexed in Scopus are computed. Naturally, the non-journal publications are excluded so there are 62,357 publications in this statistic. We see that the average percentile of publications is under 25% for all the fields.

Table 2. The output of the respondents indexed in GS and Scopus

Field	# of Respondents	Total Publications		Productivity		Year-Adjusted Citations		Average Journal Rank
		GS	Scopus	GS	Scopus	GS	Scopus	
Economics	745	33,714	14,687	4.3	1.9	4.4	3.5	0.25
Political Sci	453	22,382	8,853	4.6	1.8	3.7	3.1	0.21
Psychology	757	64,086	39,936	7.9	5.0	5.7	4.8	0.23
Sociology	376	17,392	6,689	4.4	1.7	4.6	2.8	0.24
Total	2,331	137,574	70,165	5.6	2.8	4.9	4.2	0.23

Question A. Missing from Scopus: Document type and language

2,331 respondents stated 6,979 publications as their top 3 publications. 14 publications are missing because some respondents stated only one or two publications either by choice or because they lack publications within the time frame. We could not find 132 publications (2%) in GS and 1213 publications (17%) in Scopus. 447 of the top choice, 380 of the second choice, and 386 of the third choice publications are not indexed in Scopus. Therefore, the rate of publications that are not indexed in Scopus is even more prevalent for the best publications.

An important factor that top publications are not indexed in Scopus is the document type of the publications. Scopus indexes books and book chapters as well. In fact, 9.7% of all publications in the Scopus profiles of the respondents are books and book chapters. However, the last column of Table 3 shows that 74% (row 2) of the book and 69% (row 3) of the book chapter publications cannot be found in Scopus. The ratio of the top 3 publications that are books and book chapters is relatively higher for political science and sociology (row 8). These two fields have also higher ratios of the top three publications that are not indexed in Scopus (row 10). The non-coverage problem is not contained in countries that speak a language other than English. For example, the ratio of publications that are not indexed in Scopus for US universities is only slightly lower (row 11). The non-coverage problem is not constrained to academically weaker universities. In fact, the ratio of publications of the top 50 universities is slightly below the overall figures (row 12).

Table 3. Document types of Top 3 publications

Document Type	Econ	Pol Sci	Psych	Sociology	All Fields	Not in Scopus	Not in Scopus (Ratio)
1 Article	2,080	846	2,068	753	5,747	352	0.06
2 Book	71	379	87	282	819	603	0.74
3 Book Chapter	46	108	83	84	321	222	0.69
4 Conference	19	13	18	4	54	11	0.20
5 Editorial	1	3	8	1	13	0	0.00
6 Other	10	8	4	3	25	25	1.00
7 All Documents	2,227	1,357	2,268	1,127	6,979	1,213	0.17
8 Book&Book Chapter (Ratio)	0.05	0.36	0.07	0.32	0.16		
9 Not in Scopus	198	446	205	364	1,213		
10 Not in Scopus (Ratio)	0.09	0.33	0.09	0.30	0.17		
11 Not in Scopus (Ratio-USA)	0.06	0.26	0.09	0.30	0.16		
12 Not in Scopus (Ratio-Top50)	0.05	0.25	0.08	0.29	0.15		

Scopus also indexes publications that are not in English. In fact, Scopus profiles of the respondents have 3.6% of publications that are not in English. However, Table 4 shows 83 % of the non-English top 3 publications are not indexed in Scopus. Therefore, non-English publications are largely excluded from the Scopus index. The last row shows that the respondents from economics and psychology chose 4% of their top 3 publications in a language other than English, whereas this ratio is 13% for both political science and sociology.

Table 4. Languages of Top 3 publications

Language	Econ	Political Science	Psych	Sociology	All Fields	Not in Scopus	Not in Scopus (Ratio)
English	2,146	1,178	2,166	984	6474	794	0.12
Non-English	81	179	102	143	505	419	0.83
All	2,227	1,357	2,268	1,127	6,979	1,213	0.17
Non-English (Ratio)	0.04	0.13	0.04	0.13	0.07	0.35	

In response to Question A, some respondents commented that they think that we ask for publications that are English journal articles, and so they told us that they refrained from naming non-English and book publications. We kept Question A vague in both rounds of e-mails. However, we believe that there would be more responses that contained non-English and book publications if we acknowledged the respondents that books and non-English publications are also publications.

Question A. Citation performance and journal rankings

There are extreme citation values, especially for books as more recent editions of the books accumulate citations from earlier editions. We use median instead of mean to refrain from extreme citation values. Table 5 shows the median of the citation performance adjusted by year. We see that GS citation performance is not necessarily higher for better choices. For instance, political science publications receive the highest citation performance for the third-best publications and the worst performance for the best publications. In contrast, the results are in the expected direction when we use citations from Scopus. That is, better choices receive higher citation performance.

Table 5. Median citation performance adjusted by year

Field	GS			Scopus		
	Top 1	Top 2	Top 3	Top 1	Top 2	Top 3
Economics	0.92	0.86	0.86	3.33	2.29	2.00
Political Science	0.40	0.53	0.63	4.00	3.47	2.55
Psychology	1.65	2.00	2.00	6.43	4.90	4.00
Sociology	0.67	0.92	0.80	3.33	2.80	2.29

The better choices also have higher journal percentile ranks. The top publications come from journals that are ranked 13% on average, the second-best and the third-best choices are in journals that are ranked 14% and 15% on average, respectively.

Conclusion

2,331 respondents in 42 countries provided their top 3 publications. The preliminary analysis reveals that Scopus does not cover 17% of the publications. This is mainly because many social scientists picked books and non-English publications for their top 3 publications. GS has better coverage but it has other problems such as double entries, and unreliable citation information. We show that the respondents' best choice gets better citation performance than the second and third choices in Scopus but the relationship does not hold when GS citations are used.

This is a project in progress, so we aim to complete the following additional analysis when the project is complete.

- The journals that include the top 3 publications will be compared to all journals that are in the respondents' Scopus profile. This way, we see the extent which the journal's respective subject category, publishing country, and Scimago ranking matters for the respondents' choice of top 3 publications.
- The book publications will be compared to journal publications, and we will see whether book publications are preferred given a similar citation performance.
- The properties of publications that are in the respondents' profile and have higher citation performance but are not chosen as a top 3 publication will be analyzed. The top 3 publications that are chosen despite their weak citation performance will also be analyzed.
- We will see whether biographical information is an issue in the choice of the top 3 publications. We will see whether male or female social scientists take citation performance into account more thoroughly. We will also see whether the location of PhD institution or age matters.
- We will analyze the author-order issue. We will see whether respondents chose the top 3 publications that they are the first or the last authors for non-alphabetic and alphabetic author orders.

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